

Vertical Dynamics of Flapping-Wing Flying Robot Facing Wind Disturbance: State-dependent Riccati equation and Equivalent Dynamics

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Abstract—Flapping-wing flying robots (FWFRs) are becoming a trend case study in the control field. The model of an FWFR in the gliding phase of flight is similar to an unmanned lightweight aircraft. By actuating the wings (flapping), a periodic motion disturbs the dynamics and, additionally, generates the lift and thrust forces. The actuation makes the traditional analytical dynamics complex and computationally heavy for simulations of control algorithms. In this work, the vertical dynamic of the FWFR is presented using the equivalent dynamic approach as forced base excitation. Then, a wind disturbance model is implemented to study the effect of wind gusts. The state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) method is applied to control the model for height regulation, exploiting its nonlinear-optimal capabilities on the nonlinear FWFR model and evaluating the system response to the wind disturbance. The SDRE results were compared with the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) controller. The SDRE mimics the LQR design and delivers a nonlinear version; hence, the LQR is a good candidate for comparing the results.

Keywords: Flapping wing flying robot; SDRE; FWFR; Aerial robotics; Nonlinear optimal control.

I. INTRODUCTION

The flapping-wing flying robots (FWFRs) presented complicated, unknown behavior in the dynamic studies in the literature, which made it difficult to reach a common set of equations of motion for the system. The flapping action disturbs the center-of-mass (CoM) of the robot and generates thrust/lift force. Considering the moving wings and tails as parts of a multi-body system, the degrees of freedom (DoF) of the FWFR will be increased, resulting in more complexity. This work proposes a vertical-forward dynamic derivation, adopted from the cruise flight of an aircraft. The motion of the wings will be modeled using the base-excitation approach in mechanical vibration [1], [2]. The flapping wing flight trajectories show oscillatory motion, like a persistent disturbance during the experiments to perform perching maneuvers [3], [4]. An equivalent mass-spring-damper system can model this disturbed motion to play the role of the wings and the mechanical connection to the robot's body. This approach will be used to derive the nonlinear dynamics equation of motion.

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Fig. 1. The schematic of the lateral view of an ornithopter; a representation of axes, actuation, and forces. The reference frame is the inertial-body-stability-wind reference frame.

To control the system and preserve the nonlinearity in the design, instead of using linearization methods, a nonlinear optimal control approach is employed for the height regulation of the FWFR in a forward flight. The state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) has been proven to be a popular method for various case studies, including manipulators [5], [6], mobile robots [7], satellite and spacecraft [8], [9], cable-suspended robot [10], etc.; however, this method has been desirable, specifically, for aerospace scientists, controlling multirotor systems [11], [12], aircraft [13], [14], reentry vehicle [15], etc. The SDRE has been used in flapping-wing robot control recently in simulation and indoor tested experiments [16]–[18]. The SDRE presents a quadratic cost function to weigh both error and energy, a trade-off, through weighting matrices of the optimal control. As a result, an allowable error bound can be set as the target of the control policy, and with easy tuning, the system can fulfill the task by emphasizing low energy consumption.

Flapping-wing robots are safe for interaction with people and the environment since they do not possess high-speed rotary propellers, which is common in other unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), therefore, a recent trend since 2018 has emerged in the field of flapping-wing systems. The application of the FWFR can be non-contact inspection or inspection with physical interaction. An example of non-contact inspection is monitoring using cameras while flying over a large area [19]–[21]. Sampling from the environment and nature was another application for FWFR using very lightweight robotic manipulators, 79.7(g) [22], and 94.1(g) prototype [23]. The mentioned applications motivated this work to present a simple nonlinear dynamic representation

for planner flight to assess controllers more easily and the possibility of performing comparisons with different controllers.

Wind plays an important role in the flight, dynamics, and control performance of an FWFR. It can be useful or harmful to the system. The wind is a free source of energy for gliding, an ideal situation for the robot to save significant energy; however, severe windy conditions can cancel the flight. Here in this work, the wind is modeled as a disturbance to the system to study its effect on the vertical dynamics and control. That is logical since the majority of birds also do not fly when the weather is extremely windy. Then, a wind modeling approach is studied here in this work to incorporate a wind gust model in the dynamics to see the effect and ultimate limit on wind velocity for our model and observe the reaction of the robot to the disturbance.

The main contribution of this work is to 1) present a vertical-forward dynamic representation of a flapping wing flying robot using base excitation idea, 2) incorporate a wind gust model into the system, and 3) design and implement the SDRE controller on an FWFR dynamics subjected to the wind gust.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the modeling of a wind gust. Section III shows the derivation of the FWFR dynamic modeling, adopting aircraft modeling in cruise flight and combining it with a base-excitation model in vibration. Section IV reports the control structure of the SDRE. The simulation results and data are expressed in Section V, and finally, the conclusions are reported in Section VI.

II. WIND MODEL

At this point, the atmospheric disturbance model must be implemented, hence, the following points are considered:

- P1. The aircraft is small compared to the characteristic scale of wind phenomena; that is, all parts of it are equally influenced by it.
- P2. The effect of wind disturbance is considered in the longitudinal direction.
- P3. The total wind magnitude is given by the sum of the following components:

$$V = V_{\text{avg}} + V_{\text{gust}} + V_{\text{turb}}, \quad (1)$$

where V_{avg} is a constant (average) wind speed term, V_{gust} is a discrete wind gust term, and V_{turb} is a wind turbulence or continuous gust term.

A. Discrete Wind Gust Model

Different wind gust models have been found by reviewing the literature on wind modeling in general and specifically applied to aircraft design and simulation. Two of them were more popular among researchers. The first is based on logarithmic functions, while the second uses a cosine function. Given its greater diffusion in literature, has been decided to use the cosine gust model, also because it is the one recommended by the specifications in [24] and [25], which act as a remarkable reference for the design and simulation

Fig. 2. The wind gust behavior [25].

Fig. 3. A cosine wind gust profile for an example of unit magnitude with 2 (s) duration, and wind gust starting at 6 (s).

of aircraft. This model is based on the assumption that the wind gust is discrete; therefore, it has a finite duration. This means that the wind speed output by the model will be zero for $t < T_g$ and for $t > T_{sg} + T_g$, where T_g is the gust starting time and T_{sg} is the gust duration, while in between these time instants the wind speed is:

$$V_{\text{gust}}(t) = \frac{V_m}{2} \left(1 - \cos \left\{ 2\pi \left[\frac{t}{T_g} - \frac{T_{sg}}{T_g} \right] \right\} \right),$$

where V_m is the maximum wind gust speed. The values for these parameters can be defined depending on the system model and the objective of the analysis. If the objective of the analysis is the overall validation of the aircraft, including its structural behavior, it was recommended to choose the gust duration so that the gust is tuned to the natural frequencies of the airframe and control system [24], [25]. On the other hand, the magnitude of the gust will be chosen depending on its length, following the relationship in Fig. 2 as a guide for this selection. We decided to test different values for the gust parameters. An example of the resulting wind gust profile is represented in Fig. 3.

B. Wind Turbulence Model

Wind turbulence is a complex phenomenon that is practically unfeasible to be studied with a deterministic approach; the usual way is to model it as a stochastic process with defined characteristics.

1) *White Noise*: given its stationarity, null correlation, and flat spectrum, the simplest stochastic process would be Gaussian white noise. While this is very convenient from a computational point of view, experimental results have shown how it is not appropriate to describe the real turbulence phenomena accurately. The observed probability distribution of different gust amplitudes for different frequencies highlights the necessity of non-flat probability

density spectra and non-null correlation, making the white noise a too-limited model. Both stationary and non-stationary stochastic process models have been developed for wind turbulence, but we will introduce two of the most used models for aircraft design and validation, which are the von Karman and the Dryden models, both stationary.

2) *Von Karman and Dryden Turbulence Models:* Both von Karman and Dryden models treat the gust velocities as spatially varying stochastic processes; that is, they define their power spectral density in the spatial frequency domain, knowing the speed at which the aircraft travels through the wind field. It is then easy to switch to a temporal frequency description. The von Karman model is characterized by the following power spectral density in the spatial domain:

$$\Phi(\Omega) = \sigma_u^2 \frac{2L_u}{\pi} \frac{1}{[1 + (1.339L_u\Omega)^2]^{\frac{5}{6}}}, \quad (2)$$

where σ_u is the turbulence intensity, L_u is the turbulence scale/characteristic length, and Ω is a spatial frequency. The Dryden model is instead characterized by the following power spectral density:

$$\Phi(\Omega) = \sigma_u^2 \frac{2L_u}{\pi} \frac{1}{[1 + (L_u\Omega)^2]}. \quad (3)$$

Stochastic processes responding to both models can be obtained by passing white noise through appropriate filters. Experimental results have shown how the von Karman model (2) is more accurate in the description of high-frequency phenomena, but its power spectral density results in irrational filter transfer functions, complicating its digital implementation. However, the more approximate Dryden model (3) is often used in practice, and it is approved in the literature for the assessment of the flying qualities of aircraft, so this model will be implemented in this simulation.

3) Implementation of the Dryden Turbulence Model:

As already mentioned before, a stochastic process with the power spectral density specified by the Dryden model can be obtained by passing white noise through an appropriate filter. A possible consistent realization of this filter is given by the following transfer function:

$$G(s) = \sigma_u \sqrt{\frac{2L_u}{\pi V_{\text{avg}}}} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{L_u}{V_{\text{avg}}} s},$$

which corresponds to a first-order low-pass filter, whose cut-off frequency depends on the turbulence intensity and characteristic length. A digital implementation of the filter is given by the following difference equation:

$$V_{\text{turb}}[k+1] = \left(1 - \frac{V_{\text{avg}}}{L_u} \Delta t\right) V_{\text{turb}}[k] + \sqrt{\frac{2V_{\text{avg}}}{L_u} \Delta t} \sigma_u e[k], \quad (4)$$

where w is the turbulent speed, Δt is the digital filter timestep, and e is a zero-mean, unit-variance white noise.

Fig. 4. Dryden model of the gust profile.

Fig. 5. Total wind profile for an example of average wind speed of 8 (m/s).

4) *Wind turbulence parameters:* For low-altitude flight (below 1000 ft), the specifications of MIL-F-8785C [24] give the following formulas for the selection of the turbulence intensity and scale length:

$$\begin{aligned} L_u &= \frac{h}{(0.177 + 0.000823h)^{1.2}}, \\ \frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma_w} &= \frac{1}{(0.177 + 0.000823h)^{0.4}}, \\ \sigma_w &= 0.1w_{20}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where h is the altitude in feet and w_{20} is the mean speed of the wind turbulence gust at an altitude of 20 feet. For low altitude and light intensity turbulence, $w_{20} = 10$ (knots) is set. An example of a single realization of the wind turbulence stochastic process is represented in Fig. 4. A single realization of the total wind speed profile, composed by the average speed of 8 (m/s), the gust, and the turbulence components can be found in Fig. 5.

III. DYNAMICS OF ORNITHOPTER: BASE EXCITATION

Consider the vertical-forward motion of the ornithopter, presented in Fig. 1. Based on the flight assumptions of the FWFR [2], the forward velocity is approximately constant, and consequently, it will not be included in the generalized coordinate vector. Then, the generalized coordinates of the system are $\alpha(t)$ (rad) which is the angle of attack, and $h(t)$ (m) which represents the height of the system; $\mathbf{q}(t) = [\alpha(t), h(t)]^T$, see Fig. 1. Considering the robot in gliding, the dynamic is similar to the conventional aircraft model, presented:

$$J\ddot{\alpha}(t) + bV(t)\dot{\alpha}(t) + L_w(t)d = L_E(t)l \cos E(t), \quad (6)$$

$$m\ddot{h}(t) - L_w(t) \cos \alpha(t) + L_E(t) \cos(E(t) - \alpha(t)) + mg = 0, \quad (7)$$

where J (kgm²) is the moment of inertia, $V(t)$ (m/s) is the wind speed, m (kg) is the mass of the system, d (m)

is the distance between the center of gravity (CoG) of the aircraft and center of lift of the wing, l (m) is the distance between the CoG of the system and center of lift of the elevator, E (rad) is elevator angle, and b (kgm²/s) is unsteady aerodynamics coefficient.

The lift forces of the wings $L_W(t)$ and of the elevator $L_E(t)$ are commonly expressed as a function of the air density, the aerodynamic surface area, the wind speed, and the lift coefficient, which depends on the angle of attack (AoA) on the surface, that is:

$$L(t) = \frac{1}{2}\rho C_Z(\text{AoA})SV^2(t),$$

in which the lift coefficient $C_Z(\text{AoA})$ is in general a non-linear function of the angle of attack, ρ is the air density, and S is the surface area. By introducing C_{ZE} and C_{ZW} (kgm/s²) as equivalent aerodynamics coefficients of the elevator and the wing respectively, the following expressions are obtained [26]:

$$L_W(t) = C_{ZW}V^2(t)\sin\alpha(t), \quad (8)$$

$$L_E(t) = C_{ZE}V^2(t)\sin(E(t) - \alpha(t)). \quad (9)$$

The hypothesis of a small angle of attack is used, which allows to simplify the differential equations by approximating $\cos x \approx 1$, $\sin x \approx x$, and by approximating the lift coefficient with a proportional relationship with respect to the angle of attack $C_Z(\text{AoA}) \approx C'_Z \times \text{AoA}$. The lift forces of the wings and elevator, (8) and (9), can then be expressed as:

$$L_W(t) = C_{ZW}V^2(t)\alpha(t), \quad (10)$$

$$L_E(t) = C_{ZE}V^2(t)[E(t) - \alpha(t)]. \quad (11)$$

Substituting (10) and (11) into dynamics (6) and (7) and simplification by $\cos x \approx 1$, the system is represented as

$$J\ddot{\alpha}(t) + bV(t)\dot{\alpha}(t) + (C_{ZW}d + C_{ZE}l)V^2(t)\alpha(t) = C_{ZE}IV^2(t)E(t), \quad (12)$$

$$m\ddot{h}(t) - (C_{ZW} + C_{ZE})V^2(t)\alpha(t) + mg = -C_{ZE}V^2(t)E(t). \quad (13)$$

The equilibrium position can be computed by setting the state derivative and acceleration to zero. The resulting equilibrium angle of attack and elevator deflection are:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\alpha}(t) &= \frac{mg}{C_{ZW}V^2(t)} \frac{l}{l-d}, \\ \bar{E}(t) &= \frac{C_{ZW}d + C_{ZE}l}{C_{ZE}l} \bar{\alpha}(t). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

To add the effect of flapping wings to the aircraft dynamics Eqs. (12) and (13), the concept of base excitation is used [16]. Assuming that the robot is flapping with constant frequency (approximately constant forward velocity), the flapping motion exerts a periodic oscillation to the CoG of the system that can be modeled by:

$$\begin{aligned} z_w(t) &= z_0 \sin(\omega t), \\ \dot{z}_w(t) &= z_0 \omega \cos(\omega t), \\ \ddot{z}_w(t) &= -z_0 \omega^2 \sin(\omega t), \end{aligned}$$

in which $z_w(t)$ (m) is the motion of the base, z_0 (m) is the amplitude of the base excitation, and ω (rad/s) is the flapping frequency. This motion in height can be applied through a mass-spring-damper connection to the CoG of the robot to represent (13) as:

$$\begin{aligned} m_b \ddot{h}(t) - (C_{ZW} + C_{ZE})V^2(t)\alpha(t) &= -C_{ZE}V^2(t)E(t) \\ &+ m_w \ddot{z}_w(t) + c_w \dot{z}_w(t) + k_w z_w(t) - mg, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

in which m_b (kg) is mass of the body (without wings), m_w (kg) is mass of the wings, c_w (Ns/m) is damping coefficient, k_w (N/m) is spring constant. Equation (15) shows the disturbance of the flapping wings in the dynamics, and since it is coupled with (12), the whole dynamics of the robot reflect an oscillation in the motion.

Adding the nonlinearity to the dynamic equations (12) and (15), the vertical-forward motion are rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} J\ddot{\alpha}(t) + bV(t)\dot{\alpha}(t) &+ \\ (C_{ZW}d + C_{ZE}l)V^2(t)\sin\alpha(t) &= C_{ZE}IV^2(t)E(t), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} m_b \ddot{h}(t) - (C_{ZW} + C_{ZE})V^2(t)\sin\alpha(t) &= -C_{ZE}V^2(t)E(t) \\ &+ m_w \ddot{z}_w(t) + c_w \dot{z}_w(t) + k_w z_w(t) - mg, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

which are two coupled second-order nonlinear differential equations to be controlled using the SDRE control approach. The presented model in (16) and (17) shows the behavior of the model in height and AoA. Assumption of forward flight is made to present the model and the sinusoidal terms in $z_w(t)$ and its derivatives reflect the disturbance of the flapping in the motion of the robot, based on the previous data, linked to a specific forward flight and frequency of flapping.

IV. THE SDRE METHOD

The state-dependent Riccati Equation design is a state feedback strategy in the nonlinear optimal control domain. It mimics the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) derivation; however, it accepts the system matrices to be non-linear and can, therefore, achieve better performance if the system is non-linear. In the same way as LQR, the control law is derived by minimizing a cost function, dependent on the states and on the control effort, in which the tuning parameters are the weighting matrices. For the SDRE, though, the Riccati equation solves the controller gain matrix at each time step of the simulation and releases a nonlinear input law.

Considering the state vector of the system as $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\alpha(t), h(t), \dot{\alpha}(t), \dot{h}(t)]^\top$, the generic nonlinear system (presented in Eqs. (16) and (17)) is:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\alpha}(t) \\ \dot{h}(t) \\ \frac{1}{J}(-bV(t)\dot{\alpha}(t) - (C_{ZW}d - C_{ZE}l)V^2(t)\sin\alpha(t)) \\ \frac{1}{m_b}((C_{ZW} + C_{ZE})V^2(t)\sin\alpha(t) + F_b(t) - mg) \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{J}C_{ZE}IV^2(t) \\ -\frac{1}{m_b}C_{ZE}V^2(t) \end{bmatrix} E(t), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $F_b(t) = m_w \ddot{z}_w(t) + c_w \dot{z}_w(t) + k_w z_w(t)$ is the effect of base excitation force.

The state-space representation of the dynamic (18) is a class of general nonlinear system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), t), \quad (19)$$

where the state vector can be general for a system of size $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with input vector $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and time $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Here, in this case, $n = 4$, and the system has a single input $m = 1$. $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), t) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ are vector-valued nonlinear smooth, piecewise continuous functions that satisfy local Lipschitz condition. Equation (19) is transformed into state-dependent coefficient (SDC) parameterization [27]:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\mathbf{u}(t), \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ are held. The controllability condition must hold to find a solution to the control law. The pair of $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t), t), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\}$ must shape a completely controllable parameterization of system (19) for all $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The SDC parameterization (20) for the FWFR dynamic (18) results in a disturbed system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(t)E(t) + \mathbf{d}(t), \quad (21)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} & \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x}(t)) & \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{C}(t) \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{B}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{j}C_{ZE}V_{\text{avg}}^2(t) \\ -\frac{1}{m_b}C_{ZE}V_{\text{avg}}^2(t) \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{d}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ (F_b(t) - mg)/m_b \end{bmatrix},$$

in which $\mathbf{M} = \text{diag}(J, m_b)$ and

$$\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} -(C_{ZW}d - C_{ZE}l)V_{\text{avg}}^2(t) \left(1 - \frac{\alpha(t)^2}{6} + \frac{\alpha(t)^4}{120}\right) & 0 \\ (C_{ZW} + C_{ZE})V_{\text{avg}}^2(t) \left(1 - \frac{\alpha(t)^2}{6} + \frac{\alpha(t)^4}{120}\right) & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{C}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -bV_{\text{avg}}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The following points must be considered in the SDC design:

- 1) The wind speed $V(t)$ is a result of the unknown stochastic behavior of the proposed models in Section II. It will be applied to system (18) to simulate the flight condition as close as possible to reality.
- 2) In the SDC control design (21), the unknown wind speed $V(t)$ is replaced by the average wind speed $V_{\text{avg}}(t)$; the average wind speed is considered time-varying, but in some cases it can be set to constant as well.

- 3) The gravity term and the base excitation terms, which show the effect of flapping, are collected into a disturbance vector $\mathbf{d}(t)$, and they are not considered in the SDC parameterization.
- 4) To avoid the division of $\sin \alpha(t)/\alpha(t)$ in the SDC design, Taylor series expansion of $\sin \alpha(t) = \alpha(t) - \frac{\alpha(t)^3}{6} + \frac{\alpha(t)^5}{120} - \dots$ is used.

The cost function integral of optimal control is considered as [28]:

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty \{\mathbf{x}^\top(t)\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{u}^\top(t)\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{u}(t)\} dt, \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ penalizes the states and $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ the inputs, and:

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{R}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) > \mathbf{0},$$

$$\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{Q}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \geq \mathbf{0}.$$

The sub-optimal gain $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ of the SDRE controller is found by solving the governing equation:

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)^\top \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(t)\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) + \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (23)$$

The control law of the SDRE is:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(t)\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\mathbf{x}(t). \quad (24)$$

Considering that the system has a single input $m = 1$, and the system is subjected to a disturbance vector $\mathbf{d}(t)$, the equilibrium point of the system is not zero. Then the control law (24) is rewritten as:

$$E(t) = \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(t)\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)(\mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{x}_{\text{des}}) + \hat{E}(t), \quad (25)$$

where \mathbf{x}_{des} denotes the desired states, and $\hat{E}(t)$ is the equivalent elevator input at the equilibrium point (14), but updated by the average wind speed:

$$\hat{\alpha}(t) = \frac{mg}{C_{ZW}V_{\text{avg}}^2(t)} \frac{l}{l-d},$$

$$\hat{E}(t) = \frac{C_{ZW}d + C_{ZE}l}{C_{ZE}l} \hat{\alpha}(t).$$

The stability of the SDRE can be checked using Lyapunov second's method using $V(\mathbf{x}(t), t) = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{x}^\top(t)\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t), t)\mathbf{x}(t)$ which its derivative results in negative value [27].

V. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

Consider a flapping-wing robot for the flying simulation with the expressed parameters in Table I. The system will be subjected to wind gusts as presented in the model in Section II. Here, the SDRE controller is applied to regulate the system to reach a desired set-point while the robot suffers from the disturbance. The average wind speed is $V_{\text{avg}} = 8$ (m/s), the maximum wind gust disturbance is $V_m = 2$ (m/s), gust duration is 1 (s) and it starts at second 4 of the simulation.

The flight height is considered $h = 10$ (m) which results in turbulence scale length $L_u = 67.3660$ (m), vertical turbulence

TABLE I
THE PARAMETERS OF THE SYSTEM.

parameters	value	unit	description
J	0.008	kgm^2	moment of inertia
m	0.65	kgm	mass of the system
l	0.68	m	distance between CoG body and CoL of tail
d	-0.08	m	distance between CoG body and CoL of wing
b	0.0066	kg	unsteady aerodynamics coefficient
C_{ZE}	0.2036	kg/m	aerodynamics coefficients of the elevator
C_{ZW}	1.2526	kg/m	aerodynamics coefficients of the wing
g	9.81	m/s^2	gravity constant

Fig. 6. The results of the simulation in height regulation of the FWFR with wing gust disturbance; (a) shows the angle of attack, (b) illustrates the height, and (c) shows the input signal of the elevator. The fluctuations of the tail in the disturbance zone are unrealistic for practical experimentation and must be limited to avoid damage to the actuator.

intensity $\sigma_w = 0.5144$ (m/s), and longitudinal turbulence intensity $\sigma_u = 0.9716$ (m/s), obtained from (5); units must be noticed. Then the turbulence model will be defined using (4) in which $w[t]$ delivers a filtered V_{turb} to be used in (1).

The frequency of the flapping is set $\omega = 25.1327$ (rad/s), $z_0 = 0.025$ (m), mass of wings is $m_w = 0.15$ (kg) and mass of the body is $m_b = 0.5$ (kg), elastic modulus of wing structure is defined as $E = 65 \times 10^9$ (N/m²), distance between center of gravity and wing lift force is $L = 0.25$ (m), and area moment of inertia of wing cross section is set $I = 5.1051$ (m⁴). These parameters result in an equivalent stiffness constant of the wing $k = 3EI/L^3 = 637.1150$ (N/m), and wing deflection natural frequency $\omega_n = 35.6964$ (rad/s). Setting wing deflection dimensional damping factor $\xi = 0.012$, the wing deflection damping coefficient is found $c = 2m_b\omega_n\xi = 0.4284$ (Ns/m).

The elevator motion is constrained by an upper and a lower bound $-30^\circ \leq E(t) \leq 40^\circ$. Considering the average wind speed, the equivalent AOA and the elevator position are found $\hat{\alpha} = 0.0712$ (rad) and $\hat{E} = 0.0197$ (rad), respectively. The initial condition of simulation is set as $\mathbf{x}(0) = [0.0712, 10, 0, 0]^T$ (rad, m, rad/s, m/s) which indicates initial zero velocity. The target states at the end of simulations are $\mathbf{x}(t_f) = [0.0712, 12, 0, 0]^T$ (rad, m, rad/s, m/s) which only increases the height by 2 (m). The weighting matrices are selected as $\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(0.2, 5, 0.2, 0.1)$ and $R = 5$ with 10 (s) simulation time.

The results are found in Fig. 6. The angle of attack is presented in Fig. 6-a, oscillating due to the effect of flapping but staying close to the desired equivalent angle of

Fig. 7. The comparison between the SDRE and LQR in an extreme wind gust for a lightweight FWFR, $V_m = 14$ (m/s).

attack. The height regulation is shown in Fig. 6-b, moving from 10 (m) to 12 (m) height successfully. The FWFR experienced a jump in the motion in height as a result of the wing gust. It reflected an abrupt oscillatory signal in the input signal of the elevator as well, shown in Fig. 6-c. In order to compare the results with the LQR controller, the constant parameterization of the system is required, $\{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}\}$, the coefficient of the control \mathbf{B} is already a constant matrix, then only \mathbf{A} must be linearized around the equilibrium point:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -(V_{\text{avg}}^2 \cos(\hat{\alpha})(C_{ZW}d + C_{ZE}l))/J & 0 & -V_{\text{avg}}b/J & 0 \\ (V_{\text{avg}}^2 \cos(\hat{\alpha})(C_{ZE} + C_{ZW}))/m_b & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Increasing to find gust maximum speed to 12 (m/s) and more results in complete chattering in the input signal of the elevator, which in practice fails in effective control and

also in instability of the flight. Figure 7 shows an example of $V_m = 14$ (m/s).

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

In this work, both linear and nonlinear controllers (LQR and SDRE) were applied to the system. Models for wind gusts and wind turbulence have been developed based on the literature, and the effect of wind disturbance on the system has been investigated. While the results are satisfactory, this work is based on a series of assumptions. Their relaxation could be the starting point for many future developments; here, some of them are listed. The wind models were implemented considering only the longitudinal component. A further development would be to consider the full three-dimensional wind field. This would naturally call for an extension from the study of the decoupled vertical dynamics to the coupled vertical-longitudinal dynamics, considering the effect of the wind-induced drag and the wind direction variation on the angle of attack on the disturbance rejection. Both implemented controllers, the LQR and the SDRE, used full-state feedback. It is highly unlikely that accurate measurements are available for all the states in practice, so in future studies, state observers to estimate the state from the sensor measurements could be implemented. Another development of this work could be the implementation of disturbance estimators, which could be useful in designing disturbance compensators or using robots to estimate the characteristics of the wind field by flying around an area. The Dryden turbulence model was derived for large manned aircraft flying at high speeds. An experimental validation for a small aircraft like that shown in this work should be done.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. R. Nekoo and A. Ollero, "Equivalent vertical dynamics of flapping-wing flying robot in regulation control: Displacement transmissibility ratio," in *2023 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, pp. 1301–1307, IEEE, 2023.
- [2] S. R. Nekoo and A. Ollero, "A proportional closed-loop control for equivalent vertical dynamics of flapping-wing flying robot," in *2023 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, pp. 1294–1300, IEEE, 2023.
- [3] R. Zufferey, J. Tormo-Barbero, D. Feliu-Talegón, S. R. Nekoo, J. Á. Acosta, and A. Ollero, "How ornithopters can perch autonomously on a branch," *Nature Communications*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 7713, 2022.
- [4] A. Scalvini, A. Suarez, S. R. Nekoo, and A. Ollero, "Flapping-wing aerial manipulation robot with perching-launching capabilities: Integrated modeling and control," in *Iberian Robotics conference*, pp. 98–109, Springer, 2023.
- [5] N. Nasiri, A. Fakharian, and M. B. Menhaj, "A novel controller for nonlinear uncertain systems using a combination of SDRE and function approximation technique: Regulation and tracking of flexible-joint manipulators," *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, vol. 358, no. 10, pp. 5185–5212, 2021.
- [6] A. Kabanov, V. Kramar, I. Lipko, and K. Dementiev, "Cooperative control of underwater vehicle–manipulator systems based on the SDC method," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 13, p. 5038, 2022.

- [7] N. Nasiri, A. Fakharian, and M. B. Menhaj, "A new robust control for mobile robots with differential wheels: Output-and state-dependent Riccati equation approach," in *2023 9th International Conference on Control, Instrumentation and Automation (ICCIA)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2023.
- [8] A. G. Romero and L. C. G. De Souza, "Statistical investigation about the SDRE optimality for satellites with nonlinearities," *International Journal of Applied Mathematics, Computational Science and Systems Engineering*, vol. 5, pp. 25–29, 2023.
- [9] L. C. G. de Souza, "Satellite ACS design during orbit injection using the sdre method," in *XLIV Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering*, vol. 5, 2023.
- [10] S. Omid, Y. Batmani, and S. Farhadi, "Time-varying trajectory tracking controller design for cable-suspended planar parallel robots," *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems*, vol. 108, no. 4, p. 76, 2023.
- [11] J. Yao, Z. Zhang, and G. Zhao, "Geometry enhanced finite time near optimal control strategy for acrobatic flip motion of quadcopter unmanned aerial vehicles," in *2023 62nd IEEE Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, pp. 2252–2257, IEEE, 2023.
- [12] W. Giernacki, S. Stepień, M. Chodnicki, and A. Wroblewska, "Hybrid quasi-optimal PID-SDRE quadrotor control," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 12, p. 4312, 2022.
- [13] M. Chodnicki, P. Pietruszewski, M. Wesolowski, and S. Stepień, "Finite-time SDRE control of F16 aircraft dynamics," *Archives of Control Sciences*, vol. 32, 2022.
- [14] G. P. Dos Santos, A. Kossoski, J. M. Balthazar, and A. M. Tusset, "SDRE and LQR controls comparison applied in high-performance aircraft in a longitudinal flight," *International Journal of Robotics and Control Systems*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 131–144, 2021.
- [15] D.-c. Xie, Z.-w. Wang, and W.-h. Zhang, "Attitude controller for reentry vehicles using state-dependent Riccati equation method," *Journal of Central South University*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 1861–1867, 2013.
- [16] S. R. Nekoo and A. Ollero, "Closed-loop nonlinear optimal control design for flapping-wing flying robot (1.6 m wingspan) in indoor confined space: Prototyping, modeling, simulation, and experiment," *ISA transactions*, vol. 142, pp. 635–652, 2023.
- [17] S. R. Nekoo and A. Ollero, "Experimental backward integration for state-dependent differential Riccati equation (SDDRE): A case study on flapping-wing flying robot," *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 151, p. 106036, 2024.
- [18] S. R. Nekoo and A. Ollero, "Hybrid flapping and gliding flight for robot bird using closed-loop nonlinear optimal control: Indoors experimentation," in *2024 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, pp. 129–135, IEEE, 2024.
- [19] J. P. Rodríguez-Gómez, R. Tapia, J. L. Paneque, P. Grau, A. G. Eguíluz, J. R. Martínez-de Dios, and A. Ollero, "The GRIFFIN perception dataset: Bridging the gap between flapping-wing flight and robotic perception," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 1066–1073, 2021.
- [20] E. Pan, X. Liang, and W. Xu, "Development of vision stabilizing system for a large-scale flapping-wing robotic bird," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 20, no. 14, pp. 8017–8028, 2020.
- [21] H. Huang, W. He, J. Wang, L. Zhang, and Q. Fu, "An all servo-driven bird-like flapping-wing aerial robot capable of autonomous flight," *IEEE/ASME transactions on mechatronics*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 5484–5494, 2022.
- [22] S. R. Nekoo, D. Feliu-Talegón, J. A. Acosta, and A. Ollero, "A 79.7 g manipulator prototype for E-Flap robot: A plucking-leaf application," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 65300–65308, 2022.
- [23] S. R. Nekoo, D. Feliu-Talegón, R. Tapia, A. C. Satue, J. R. Martínez-de Dios, and A. Ollero, "A 94.1 g scissors-type dual-arm cooperative manipulator for plant sampling by an ornithopter using a vision detection system," *Robotica*, vol. 41, no. 10, pp. 3022–3039, 2023.
- [24] M. Specification, "Flying qualities of piloted airplanes," tech. rep., MIL-F-8785C, 1980.
- [25] M. Specification, "Department of defense handbook: Flying qualities of piloted airplanes," tech. rep., MIL-HDBK-1797, 2004.
- [26] J.-J. E. Slotine, W. Li, *et al.*, *Applied nonlinear control*, vol. 199. Prentice hall Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1991.
- [27] S. R. Nekoo, "Tutorial and review on the state-dependent Riccati equation," *Journal of Applied Nonlinear Dynamics*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 109–166, 2019.
- [28] H. Banks, B. Lewis, and H. T. Tran, "Nonlinear feedback controllers and compensators: A state-dependent Riccati equation approach," *Computational Optimization and Applications*, vol. 37, pp. 177–218, 2007.